

Evaluating the Performance of AI Models Under Multiple Criteria

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Abstract

The evaluation of a model performance has traditionally been performed by staff with quantitative skills. As organizations increasingly rely on AI models to support business applications or to inform their decisions, more stakeholders will undeniably be interested in whether the performance of these models is meeting their individual criteria. In Salami et al (2023) [1], we considered two stakeholders including the model owner¹ and the model developer² having two different success criteria; and we showed that linking the performance metrics they care about can enable a more effective evaluation of the model during the monitoring phase. In this paper, we propose to expand this linkage to the development phase to identify which model meets these two success criteria hence should be selected for deployment. Moreover, we propose a methodology to optimize the relationship between the performance metrics of these two stakeholders. Finally, we show how the lack of understanding of the business context can lead to the selection of an inadequate statistical performance metric, which can lead to erroneous decisions with severely adverse business impact depending on the model applications.

Key Words: artificial intelligence, machine learning, multivariate statistical process control, model monitoring, monitoring thresholds, false discovery rate, hypothesis testing, control charts.

1. Introduction

Organizations have been using quantitative models to inform or support decisions for decades. Initially developed in 1960s, the Capital Asset Pricing Model (CAPM) has been widely used to help relate the required return on an investment to the risk of that investment [2]. The release of the FICO score in 1990s has helped generalize the use of quantitative models in consumers' credit risk assessment [3].

In these cases, and many others, the appeal of the quantitative models lies on the promise that they can provide a data-driven, rational, and consistent approach to business decision-making. Given the recent emergence and popularity of artificial intelligence (AI) systems, and their ability to use powerful algorithms to process large quantity of data, the reliance on quantitative methods to inform or support decisions will only increase across organizations. However, the communication between the data scientist developing the model and the business leaders commissioning or using the model is often limited to the collection of high-level business requirements and a limited understanding of the business process that is being represented by the model.

In this paper, we argue that this limited communication can lead to ineffective models that may not suit their purpose. During the model development phase, data scientists should not work in silos with limited information about the business process they are modeling. Rather, they should work closely with the model's owner and users to clearly understand how they define success for their business process and incorporate this definition in the model evaluation.

¹ The business team who commissioned the model development. This team owns the model risk.

² The data scientist who developed the model

2. Literature Review

Research on model evaluation covers various methodologies often employed to assess the acceptability of the model output. Whether the model evaluation involves back-testing, sensitivity analysis, scenario analysis or stress testing many researchers often rely on generic statistical performance metrics, some of which are described in sections 2.1 below. But these researchers often omit to mention how these statistical performance metrics can differ from the business key performance indicators (KPI) that measure success from the business leaders' perspective. This omission reflects a serious misalignment of incentives that may occur between the objectives of the model developer and the model's owner and users. This paper is trying to address this misalignment.

2.1 Statistical Performance Metrics

The statistical metrics required to evaluate a model performance often depend on the model types. In general, models can be grouped into two broad categories namely classification and regression models. In this paper, we will focus on classification models.

Classification models are used to predict outcomes that are categorical in nature. An example of classification model is one that predicts whether a customer applying for a financial product (credit card, deposit, or loan account etc.) should be approved or rejected. For such models, the literature recommends several statistical performance metrics to evaluate how well the model can distinguish between the possible categories (approved or rejected, in this case).

For a binary classifier (i.e. two possible categories), the following metrics are often recommended:

- $Recall = \frac{t_p}{t_p + f_n}$ (1)
- $Precision = \frac{t_p}{t_p + f_p}$ (2)
- $Accuracy (ACC) = \frac{t_p + t_n}{t_p + f_p + t_n + f_n}$ (3)

where t_p , f_p , t_n , and f_n are the numbers of true positives, false positives, true negatives, and false negatives, respectively, and

- $F_1 = 2 * \frac{Precision * Recall}{Precision + Recall}$ (4)

Additional metrics include:

- the area under the receiver operating curve (AUROC)
- the area under the precision-recall curve (AUPRC).

2.2 Business Key Performance Indicators

The data scientist(s) who developed a model are in most cases not its primary users. Like a software developer whose product is often consumed by staff with varying level of coding skills, the data scientists develop models that are often used by staff with limited to no quantitative skills to help meet a broader business objective. In fact, in many business organizations, the model output is just one out of several pieces of information that contribute to the final outcome, be it prediction, recommendation, or decision; see figure 0 below.

Figure 0: Models in business decision-making

As such, the indicators of success that appeal to the business leaders (criterion #1) can be very different from the statistical performance metrics (criterion #2) that the data scientists care about.

Examples of KPIs	
Business Objective	Business KPI
Reduce credit card fraud risk	Credit card fraud loss
Improve customer satisfaction	Net promoter Score
Increase staff retention	Employee Survey Score

Table 1: Examples of KPI Setting

Table 1 shows examples of KPI corresponding to some business objectives. For example, to meet the business objective of reducing credit card fraud risk, the business leaders may track credit card loss amount (criterion #1) whereas the data scientists would be more interested in the model's discriminatory power i.e., the model's ability to distinguish a valid transaction from a fraudulent one (criterion #2).

3. Our Proposal

The use of different performance metrics by the data scientists and the business leaders is a problem that can have serious consequences for the business when these metrics contradict each other. From the data scientists who may spend significant amount of time and resources in roots cause analysis to the business leaders who may embark in uninformed post-model adjustments, lack of trust in the model output can become the central issue. To remedy this problem, this paper proposes to establish a relationship between the model's statistical performance metric (criterion #2) and the business KPI (criterion #1) such that deterioration or improvement in the business KPI can be traced back to the model.

4. An Illustrative Example

4.1 Model Description

Credit card fraud is a serious problem for banks and other lenders. A 2021's report by the Federal Trade Commission found credit card fraud to be the second most reported identity theft type in the U.S behind government documents and benefits fraud [4]. Nilson, a leading publication covering payment systems estimated the losses associated with credit card fraud to be \$32 billion worldwide, \$12 billion of which were incurred in the US in 2021 [5]. It follows that detecting and preventing credit card fraud is a top risk management objective for card's issuers and processors as well as merchants.

In this paper, we illustrate our proposal with credit card fraud data publicly available on Kaggle.com. The anonymized dataset, released by Vesta Corporation as part of an open data science competition can be summarized as follows:

- Number of unique transactions: 590,540 including 20,663 fraud cases
- 394 variables including transaction status, transaction date, product code, transaction amount, IP address, number of days between transactions and more.
- The target variable is the transaction status, labeled as “IsFraud”. It takes the value:
 - 1 if the transaction is fraudulent.
 - 0 otherwise.

After data preparation and cleaning, we split the dataset into training data (53%), out-of-sample or test data (23%) and out-of-time or monitoring data (24%).

Then, through feature engineering, we reduced the number of variables from 394 to 48.

Finally, we fit the following random forest classifier after a model selection process described in Appendix 1.

```
rf_max6 = RandomForestClassifier(max_depth = 6, random_state = 42)
```

4.2. Model Outcome Analysis

The performance of the fitted random forest algorithm on the training data can be summarized as follows:

Metric	AUPRC	F1_Score	Precision	Recall
Test Data	0.12	0.91	0.96	0.88

Table 2: Performance of rf_max6

Out of the four metrics in the table 2 above we will focus on the F1_score and the AUPRC. Indeed, due to the severance imbalance³ in the credit card fraud use case data, these two metrics are often considered to be more appropriate than the Precision and Recall because they account for both precision and recall metrics.

In general, when the model’s statistical performance is reasonably strong and/or better than that of the available alternative (criterion #1), the model is approved for continued use. In Salami et al (2023), we noted that during the model monitoring phase, this basis for accepting the continued model use is insufficient as it completely ignores the business KPI which reflects the business leaders’ gauge of the model effectiveness. In this paper, we argue that this insufficiency should also be noted during the model development phase. In other words, the evaluation of the model performance during the model development phase should not be guided by only the criterion #1 but should also meet the criterion #2 (i.e. the business KPI is also satisfactory). Otherwise, the consequences can involve significant waste of time, resources or significant financial loss depending on the model’s applications. To solve this issue, we propose to expand the linkage of the statistical performance to the business KPI during monitoring (see Salami et al (2023) [1]) to the evaluation of the model during the development phase.

4.3. Linking the statistical performance to the business KPI

The business leaders, in their capacity of model owner in many organisations, often hold a higher authority over the data scientist as to whether the model is meeting the target business objective. Therefore, **we consider the business KPI to be a constraint**. Then, the task becomes to find a statistical performance metric that can concur with this business KPI such that an improvement or deterioration in the business KPI can be traced back to the model. Let’s illustrate our proposal with the credit card fraud use case described in section 4.1.

³ The proportion of fraud cases is 3.5% which is very small and indicative of an imbalanced dataset.

Let consider the following hypothetical cost structure 1 which describes the average business cost associated with the model error as evaluated by the business leaders:

Cost structure 1: FP more costly than FN

- \$0 = cost of a True negative or TN (the model accurately identifies a valid transaction)
- \$3 = cost of a False Negative or FN (the model flags a fraudulent transaction as valid)
- \$0 = cost of a True Positive or TP (the model accurately flags a fraudulent transaction)
- \$60⁴ = cost of a False Positive or FP (the model flags a valid transaction as fraudulent)

We can then compute for a given data sample⁵, the statistical performance metric value, and the associated business cost in terms of loss amount from credit card fraud. The figure 1 below shows the relationship between these two performance measures.

Figure 1: Relationship between credit card fraud loss amount and AUPRC in cost structure 1

The expectation in linking the statistical performance metric (x-axis) to the business KPI (y-axis) is to establish a monotonic relationship between these two measures. For the fraud use case under study, this monotonic relationship would signal that a decrease in the fraud loss amount would correspond to an increase in the model’s performance.

For AUPRC as the measure of the model’s statistical performance, while the Figure 1 above shows the expected negative relationship, the monotonic relationship with the fraud loss amount is rather weak as measured by the 15.68% R^2 . At first, this result may be surprising considering that the AUPRC is often recommended when measuring the performance of a binary classifier on severely imbalanced data like the credit card data under consideration.

But, as we revisit the definition of the AUPRC, we realize that this metric is mainly focused on the positive class [5], which may explain why it does not show the strong monotonic relationship we are seeking with the business KPI. To proceed, we investigate the second statistical performance measure in Table 2, namely the F1_score, which is also recommended for imbalance data (see footnote 7).

⁴ In reality, FN are more costly than FP in the case of credit card fraud as discussed in section 5.2.

⁵ The modeling data are grouped in 36 samples by order of time of transaction, each containing 12,500 credit card transactions.

Figure 2: Relationship between credit card fraud loss amounts and F1_score in cost structure 1

Figure 2 shows the same negative relationship but also a stronger monotonic and linear relationships between the fraud loss amounts and F1_score than that observed between the same fraud loss amounts and AUPRC in Figure 1. This is an encouraging observation considering that the F1_score is a particular form of F_β score⁶ [6]. In general, for each of the binary classes:

$$F_\beta = (1 + \beta^2) * \frac{\text{precision} * \text{recall}}{(\beta^2 * \text{precision}) + \text{recall}} \quad \text{Equation 5}$$

In particular:

$$\beta = 1: F_1 = (1 + 1^2) * \frac{\text{precision} * \text{recall}}{(1^2 * \text{precision}) + \text{recall}} = 2 * \frac{\text{precision} * \text{recall}}{\text{precision} + \text{recall}} = \frac{2}{\frac{1}{\text{recall}} + \frac{1}{\text{precision}}} \quad \text{Equation 5.1}$$

$$\beta = 2: F_2 = (1 + 2^2) * \frac{\text{precision} * \text{recall}}{(2^2 * \text{precision}) + \text{recall}} = 5 * \frac{\text{precision} * \text{recall}}{(4 * \text{precision}) + \text{recall}} = \frac{5}{\frac{4}{\text{recall}} + \frac{1}{\text{precision}}} \quad \text{Equation 5.2}$$

...and so on:

- $F_\beta \rightarrow \text{precision}$ if $\beta \rightarrow 0$ Equation 5.3
- $F_\beta \rightarrow \text{recall}$ if $\beta \rightarrow \infty$ Equation 5.4.

When we investigate the relationship between the fraud loss amounts and F_β for different values of β , we observe an interesting trend as shown in figure 4 below⁷.

⁶ In F_β , β indicates the magnitude by which Recall is given more importance than Precision.

⁷ It is important to note that, due to the severe imbalance in the data, the F_β values shown in this paper are calculated in Python scikit learn with the average option = "weighted" in $F_\beta = \text{fbeta_score}(y_true, y_pred, *, \text{beta}, \text{labels}=\text{None}, \text{pos_label}=1, \text{average}=\text{'weighted'}, \text{sample_weight}=\text{None}, \text{zero_division}=\text{'warn'})$, see [9] for more information.

Figure 3: Relationship between fraud loss amount and various forms of F_β in cost structure 1

Figure 3 shows the monotonic relationship with a downward slope that we are seeking. For the credit card fraud use case; this relationship is linear and gets stronger from F1_score to F4_score as illustrated by the regression's R^2 and slope. In Salami et al (2023), we acknowledged that while we can investigate the strength of this relationship for higher values of β until the R^2 peaks, we stopped at $\beta = 3^8$ and concluded that the F_3 is an appropriate statistical performance measure to link to the business KPI for monitoring purpose i.e. F_3 is well-suited to evaluate both the model's statistical and business performance.

In the current paper, we argue that the search for the well-suited statistical measure to link to the business KPI should not be limited to the model monitoring phase but should also be considered during the model development phase. In addition, we explore the possibility of higher values of R^2 for β values greater than 4.

5. Model Evaluation During the Development Phase

There are two main observations that can be drawn from Figures 1 through 4. In figure 1, we observe that while, in general, the AUPRC could fulfill the criterion # 1 (i.e. compare this model's statistical performance to that of an alternative) it is not well-suited for criterion #2 (i.e. use the model's statistical performance to explain the variation in the business KPI). As such an improvement or deterioration in the business KPI could not be clearly attributed to the model's statistical performance if we select the AUPRC.

The second observation can be drawn from figure 3 and 4. For this credit card fraud use case, the F_β score is better suited to fulfill criteria #1 and #2 than the AUPRC. It also has the advantage to be more flexible than the AUPRC as β can take on different values to better respond to the changing difference between the weight (or cost) assigned to the model errors reflected by the false positives and false negatives outcomes.

⁸ Because $F_{\beta=3}$ already yields a strong relationship with $R^2 = 96\%$ and the latter does not materially change from $\beta = 3$ to $\beta = 4$ (as $R^2_3 = 0.9639 \sim R^2_4 = 0.9713$)

Now that we identified the F_β as the more suitable statistical metric to link to the business KPI in this credit card fraud case, the question becomes which value of β can optimize this link. In other words, for which value of β is the R^2 the highest between F_β and the credit card fraud loss amount.

5.1. Finding the Optimal β

Recall that in linking the model's statistical performance metric to the business KPI our objective is to quantify the importance that the model plays in achieving the business outcome for which it was developed.

Let:

- F_β is the best metric for measuring the model's statistical performance.
- KPI is the best metric for measuring the model's business outcome.
- f the link function such that $KPI = f(F_\beta)$

The first step in finding the optimal β is to specify the function f . This can be done through a scatter plot that shows the F_β on the x-axis and the KPI on the y-axis. This function f will depend on the use case under review. For the credit card fraud use case described in section 4.1, f appears to be linear based on the plots in figure 3. Therefore, we can specify f using the ordinary least squares method as follows:

$$\widehat{KPI}_i = a_i * F_\beta + b_i, \quad \text{where } i \text{ is a data sample}^9; \beta \in \mathbb{R} \text{ (equation 6)}$$

The second step is to select a measure of fit.

In the credit card fraud use case, given f is linear, it is appropriate to select the coefficient of determination R_β^2 to estimate the proportion of the variation in the fraud loss amount explained by the model's statistical performance, F_β . As shown in figure 3, for each value of β we can calculate R_β^2 as follows:

$$R_\beta^2 = 1 - \frac{SS_{res}}{SS_{TOT}} = 1 - \frac{\sum_i (y_i - \hat{y}_i)^2}{\sum_i (y_i - \bar{y})^2} = 1 - \frac{\sum_i (KPI_i - \widehat{KPI}_i)^2}{\sum_i (KPI_i - \bar{KPI}_i)^2} \text{ (equation 7)}$$

The third step is to solve for the optimal β value. To do so, we plot the R_β^2 against each of the corresponding β values as shown in figures 4 below.

Figure 4: Relationship between β and R_β^2 in cost structure 1 for $\beta \geq 1$

⁹ Recall that we divided the training data into n ($=36$) samples. For each sample i , the model performance F_β and the corresponding business performance KPI_i are calculated. To construct the charts in Figure 4, we plotted the F_β on the X-axis and the KPI_i on the Y-axis.

There are several points that we can make from Figure 4. The first point is that, in cost structure 1, **the most-suited metric to evaluate the performance of this model conditional to the business KPI is neither F_3 nor F_4** . Note that in Salami et al (2023), we stopped at $\beta = 3$ because we found the $R_{\beta=3}^2 = 0.96387$ to be sufficiently high and very close to $R_{\beta=4}^2 = 0.97135$. Figure 4 shows that, for $\beta > 4$, we can find a higher R^2 as illustrated by $R_{\beta=29}^2 = 0.97596$.

The second point comes from figure 5 below which shows that **the relationship between β and R_{β}^2 is not strictly increasing monotonic** as it might be tempting to infer from figure 3. Note that the values of β in figure 4 are greater or equal to 1. But they don't have to be. To the extent that β indicates the magnitude by which Recall is given more importance than Precision we can extend the β values range to 0 and beyond 30.75 (which is the last value of β in figure 4).

Figure 5: Relationship between β and R_{β}^2 in cost structure 1 for $\beta \geq 0$

We observe a decreasing relationship between β and R_{β}^2 for $\beta \in [0,1[$ in figure 5 as well as for large values of β shown in Table 3 below.

β	R_{β}^2
331	0.9759639120
500	0.9759639093
600	0.9759639087
631	0.9759639085
700	0.9759639083
800	0.9759639080
900	0.9759639079
931	0.9759639078
1,000	0.9759639077
1,231	0.9759639075
1,531	0.9759639074

Table 3: Values of R_{β}^2 for large values of β for cost structure 1

Given this lack of strict monotonicity and the decreasing values of R_{β}^2 corresponding to the large values of β in table 3 and noting that F_{∞} **should approximate** the Recall metric (equation 5.4), we measured the strength of the linear relationship between the Recall metric and the fraud loss amount, we obtain $R_{Recall}^2 = 0.9759639072$. In other words, in cost structure 1, the recall metric does not have the strongest linear relationship with the fraud loss amount as R_{Recall}^2 is lower than the R_{β}^2 values in table 3.

That said, it can be argued that $R_{Recall}^2 = 0.9759639072 \approx 0.98$ is sufficiently close to 1, the maximum possible R^2 value. In addition, the Recall metric, defined in this use case as the proportion of actual fraudulent transactions identified by the model, has a more intuitive business meaning than $F_{\beta_{opt}}$ (the metric corresponding to the optimal β). **Therefore, we can make the third point i.e. in this cost structure 1, that is, the Recall metric is a reasonable approximation of $F_{\beta_{opt}}$.**

The relationship between the β and the R_{β}^2 in figure 5 is based on the business context summarized by the cost structure 1 in section 4.3. But in reality, the cost structure is likely to differ across types, location, or time of the credit card transactions. In the section 5.2 below, we explore a different cost structure.

5.2. Influence of the business context

The cost structure 1 assumes that the business cost of a false positive (FP) is 20 times that of a false negative (FN). For the credit card fraud use case the inverse is more likely as the financial loss resulting from the occurrence of fraud is much greater than that resulting from declining a valid transaction based on fraud suspicion. For illustration purpose, let us consider the following cost structure 2 in which a FN costs 20 times a FP:

Cost structure 2:

- \$0 = cost of a True negative or TN (the model accurately identifies a valid transaction)
- \$60 = cost of a False Negative or FN (the model flags a fraudulent transaction as valid)
- \$0 = cost of a True Positive or TP (the model accurately flags a fraudulent transaction)
- \$3 = cost of a False Positive or FP (the model flags a valid transaction as fraudulent)

The link between the β values and the R_{β}^2 in the cost structure 2 is shown in figure 6 below.

Figure 6: Relationship between β and R_{β}^2 in cost structure 2 for $\beta \geq 0$

When we change the business context (from cost structure 1 to cost structure 2), the Recall is no longer the most-suited metric. Instead, R_{β}^2 is maximum at $\beta = 0$, meaning the Precision metric

becomes the most-suited metric to evaluate the performance of this model in this new business context despite no change to the model's data or methodology. At first, these results may appear to be intuitive. After all, these two metrics are among the generic performance measures populated by packages in Python or R and widely used by data scientists. At question is whether there is a scenario in which a statistical performance metric other than Recall or Precision is better suited to explain the variation in the business KPI. We explore these scenarios in section 5.2.1 below.

5.2.1 Beyond Precision and Recall

The relationship between β and R_β^2 illustrated by figures 5 and 6 above were based on scenarios that can be summarized as follows:

Let $w(X)$

$w(X)$, the weight or cost assigned to X.

$w(X/Y) = \frac{w(X)}{w(Y)}$, the weight ratio between X and Y

In cost structure 1, where $w(FP/FN) = 20$, Recall was selected as the most-suited metric

In cost structure 2, where $w(FN/FP) = 20$, Precision was selected as the most-suited metric

Now let's consider the cost structure 3 in which the weight ratio is different from 20.

Cost structure 3:

- \$0 = cost of a True negative or TN (the model accurately identifies a valid transaction)
- \$50 = cost of a False Negative or FN (the model flags a fraudulent transaction as valid)
- \$0 = cost of a True Positive or TP (the model accurately flags a fraudulent transaction)
- \$5 = cost of a False Positive or FP (the model flags a valid transaction as fraudulent)

Figure 7 shows the relationship between β and R_β^2 when the weight ratio is 10 in favor of the FN.

Figure 7: Relationship between β and R_β^2 in cost structure 3 for $\beta \geq 0$

Figure 7 shows that it is possible to obtain an optimal β value that is neither 0 nor too large ($\neq \infty$). In this cost structure 3, the most-suited metric to evaluate the statistical and the business performance of the model is $F_{0.25}$. In other words, in cost structure 3, when the cost of FN is 10 times that of the FP then the Recall metric is a quarter as important as the Precision.

Let's further reduce the weight difference between the FN and the FP. Consider the cost structure 4 below in which the weight ratio (FN/FP) is reduced to 5 from 10 in cost structure 3.

Cost structure 4:

- \$0 = cost of a True negative or TN (the model accurately identifies a valid transaction)
- \$40 = cost of a False Negative or FN (the model flags a fraudulent transaction as valid)
- \$0 = cost of a True Positive or TP (the model accurately flags a fraudulent transaction)
- \$8 = cost of a False Positive or FP (the model flags a valid transaction as fraudulent)

Figure 8: Relationship between β and R^2_β in cost structure 5 for $\beta \geq 0$

The above figure 8 is another example of scenarios in which the most-suited metric to evaluate the statistical performance of the model is not the Recall or the Precision metric. In cost structure 4, when the weight ratio is 5 in favor of the FN, then the Recall metric is three-quarter as important as the Precision metric and $F_{0.75}$ is the most-suited metric to evaluate the model's statistical and business performance.

5.2.2 Approximation of Infinity

Throughout this paper, we illustrated our proposal with the same credit card transaction data and the same model. Yet, we found that the most-suited metric to evaluate the model's statistical and business performance differs from one cost structure to the other. In particular cost structures 3 and 4 show that statistical metrics other than the commonly used precision, recall, AUPRC or F1 score could be best suited to both evaluate the model's statistical performance and explain the variation in the business KPI. This finding underscores the importance of understanding and accounting for the business context in the evaluation of a model performance. Failure to do so can lead to selecting a model whose performance may not be an accurate reflection of that of the business KPI, which can lead to the continued use of an ineffective model or the premature retirement of the model.

5. Conclusion and next steps

This paper concurs with our previous findings in Salami et al (2023) [1] and argues that evaluating the performance of a model based on statistical metrics alone has limitations as models do not exist in isolation but operate within a broader business context. In addition, in this paper we show that accounting for the business KPI in the evaluation of the model performance should be extended beyond the model monitoring phase to the model development phase to inform the selection of a model among candidates. Provided the linkage between the business KPI and the model's statistical performance metric can be approximated by a function, it ensues that optimizing this function becomes essential to find the optimal statistical metric. We illustrated our proposal using the F_β measure and showed how to approximate the optimal β value in various business contexts.

In this paper, we assumed that the model is the only factor that influences the business KPI hence our function was univariate. In reality, the business KPI is often influenced by many other factors as illustrated by Figure 0, Therefore, our work can be further enhanced by considering multivariate functions that incorporate the model and these other key factors that influence the business KPI amid data availability. When possible, one may optimize and measure the business KPI directly (see, for example, Lo & Pachamano (2023) [8]).

Appendix 1: Model selection

The random forest rf_max6 was selected over the other two candidates due to its higher precision, recall or F1:

- DTC_ent5 = DecisionTreeClassifier (criterion= 'entropy', max_depth=5, random_state=42)
- LR = LogisticRegression (random_state=42)

Scorer/Metric	0	1	Accuracy	Macro avg	Weighted avg	Classifier
precision	0.98	0.14	0.86	0.56	0.96	DTC_ent5
Recall	0.86	0.63	0.86	0.75	0.86	DTC_ent5
F1_score	0.92	0.23	0.86	0.58	0.90	DTC_ent5
precision	0.98	0.13	0.88	0.56	0.95	Lr_lbfgs
Recall	0.90	0.43	0.88	0.66	0.88	Lr_lbfgs
F1_score	0.94	0.20	0.88	0.57	0.91	Lr_lbfgs
precision	0.99	0.17	0.88	0.58	0.96	Rf_max6
Recall	0.89	0.63	0.88	0.76	0.88	Rf_max6
F1_score	0.94	0.27	0.88	0.60	0.91	Rf_max6

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